

Uncertainty estimation of AOD for PMOD PFR, CIMEL CE318, and Prede POM sunphotometers

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Introduction

This document contains a comprehensive uncertainty estimate of spectral AOD retrieved from solar irradiance measurements using narrowband filter radiometers. The uncertainty estimation is aimed at reference radiometers. The uncertainty of AOD obtained from instruments operated operationally in a network will be included at a later stage. The uncertainty estimations is specifically aimed at the three main aerosol monitoring networks GAWPFR, AERONET, SKYNET.

Measurement equation

The spectral AOD is calculated using the Beer-Lambert law as,

$$\tau_{aod} = \left[\log \left(\frac{I_c}{I_0} \right) + \left(\tau_{ray} m_{ray} + \sum_i \tau_i m_i \right) \right] / m$$

Where $I_c = I \cdot (1 - I_{Cleaning}^{rel} - I_{FOV_{strl}}^{rel} - I_{Clouds}^{rel})$

Expanded to explicitly mention all main gases, yields the measurement equation for AOD,

$$\tau_{aod} = \left[\log(I) - \log(I_0) + \left(XS_{ray} m_{ray} P / P_0 + \tau_{NO_2} m_{NO_2} + \tau_{O_3} m_{O_3} + \tau_{H_2O} m_{H_2O} + \tau_{CO_2,CH_4} m_{CO_2,CH_4} \right) \right] / m$$

Where $\tau_{TraceGas} = TC_{TraceGas} XS_{TraceGas}$

Where the wavelength term has been omitted for simplicity.

- I is the measured direct solar irradiance I (signal or calibrated) corrected for the contributions of cleaning efficiency $I_{Cleaning}^{rel}$, straylight in the FOV of the instrument $I_{FOV_{strl}}^{rel}$ and attenuation due to clouds I_{Clouds}^{rel} .
 - I_0 is the solar irradiance at the top of the atmosphere
 - τ_{ray} is the optical depth of Rayleigh scattering
 - m_{ray} is the airmass for Rayleigh scattering
 - τ_{NO_2} is the optical depth of nitrogen dioxide
 - m_{NO_2} is the airmass for nitrogen dioxide
 - τ_{O_3} is the ozone optical depth
 - τ_{H_2O} is the optical depth of water vapor, corrected at 1020 nm and 1640 nm (CIMEL radiometer)
 - τ_{CO_2,CH_4} is the optical depth of CO₂-CH₄, corrected at 1640 nm (CIMEL radiometer)
 - m_{H_2O} is the airmass for water vapor
 - $m_{CO_2-CH_4}$ is the airmass for CO₂-CH₄
 - m_{O_3} is the ozone airmass
 - m is the aerosol airmass
-
- P is the pressure at the site
 - P_0 is the pressure at 1 atm, 1013.25 mbar
 - $TC_{TraceGas}$ total column of trace gas
 - $XS_{TraceGas}$ trace gas absorption cross-section weighted by the normalized measured or assumed responsivity of the filter with centroid wavelength λ

Sensitivity components

The sensitivity components are:

Irradiance	Optical path - Airmass $\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial m_{TraceGas}} = \frac{\tau_{TraceGas}}{m}$	Trace Gases Concentration/ Total column $\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial \tau_{TraceGas}} = \frac{m_{TraceGas}}{m}$	Wavelength offset and filter function
$\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial I} = \frac{1}{I} \cdot \frac{1}{m}$	$\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial m_{ray}} = \frac{\tau_{ray}}{m}$ $= \frac{XS_{ray} P}{m P_0}$	$\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial \tau_{ray}} = \frac{m_{ray}}{m}$ Where $\partial \tau_{ray} = \frac{XS_{ray}}{P_0} \partial P$ Or $\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial P} = \frac{XS_{ray} m_{ray}}{m} \frac{1}{P_0}$	$\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial XS_{ray}} = \frac{m_{ray} P}{m P_0}$

$\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial I_{Cleaning}^{rel}} = \frac{1}{I} \cdot \frac{1}{m}$	$\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial m_{O3}} = \frac{\tau_{O3}}{m}$	$\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial \tau_{O3}} = \frac{m_{O3}}{m}$	$\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial XS_{O3}} = \frac{m_{O3}}{m} TC_{O3}$
$\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial I_{FOV_{strl}}^{rel}} = \frac{1}{I} \cdot \frac{1}{m}$	$\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial m_{NO2}} = \frac{\tau_{NO2}}{m}$	$\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial \tau_{NO2}} = \frac{m_{NO2}}{m}$	$\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial XS_{NO2}} = \frac{m_{NO2}}{m} TC_{NO2}$
$\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial I_{Clouds}^{rel}} = \frac{1}{I} \cdot \frac{1}{m}$
$\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial I_0} = \frac{1}{I_0} \cdot \frac{1}{m}$	$\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial m} = \frac{\tau_{aod}}{m}$		

Uncertainty components

The following sections are separated for the three networks, and can be expanded depending on the needs. The uncertainty budget is then calculated from the individual uncertainty components according to

$$u = \sqrt{\sum_i \left(\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_i} \right) \cdot u_{xi} \right)^2}$$

The partial derivatives for u_{xi} are as defined above.

GAWPFR- Precision filter radiometer

1) Direct solar irradiance measurement I

The measurement uncertainty u_i is composed of the uncertainty of the data acquisition unit u_{daq} , the uncertainty in the dark signal, u_{dark} , the standard deviation of the measurements, u_{std} , the electronic stability of the instrument and the DAQ system u_{ref} 2.5V and the uncertainty $u_{FOV-Hom}$ associated with the pointing tolerance of 10 arcmin from the centre of the plateau in conjunction with the field of view homogeneity of 1%. For the PFRs operated within the GAWPFR network, typical values are $u_{daq}=10^{-6}$ V, $u_{dark}=3 \cdot 10^{-6}$ V, $u_{std}=0.01$ %. For $u_{FOV-Hom}$ it is assumed that the uncertainties are maximum limits (rectangular distribution), so $u_{FOV-Hom} = 0.5/\sqrt{3}$ %.

The average signal level is of the order of $S=2.0$ V, and 10 measurements (N) are acquired to form an average value, the relative standard measurement uncertainty u_I is:

$$u_I = \sqrt{\left[\frac{u_{daq}}{S} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{u_{dark}}{S} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{u_{std}}{100\sqrt{N}} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{u_{FOV-Hom}}{100} \right]^2} = 0.0029$$

u_{daq}	u_{dark}	u_{std}	$u_{FOV-Hom}$
10^{-6} V	$3E-6$ V	0.01 %	$0.5/\sqrt{3}$ %

2) Top of atmosphere solar irradiance

The top-of-atmosphere irradiance value is retrieved by the Langley extrapolation procedure of several days of measurements. PFR Langley are performed in a 6-month period. This aims in increasing the number of Langley days in the statistics, based on the fact that instruments have negligible change in responsivity within this period. The average number of points used is in the order of 70. Based on Eq.

1 the AOD uncertainty, that is related only to the Langley calibration factor I_0 , equals $\frac{u_{\ln(I_0)}}{m}$ where $u_{\ln(I_0)}$ is the uncertainty of Napierian logarithm of I_0 defined by the Langley extrapolation or the relative uncertainty of I_0 , $u_{\ln(I_0)} = \frac{a u_{I_0}}{I_0} = u_{I_0}$. The uncertainty of $\ln(I_0)$ can be described by the coefficient of variation (standard deviation / mean, (CV)) column 2 of next table) or in the case of a normal distribution by the standard error (standard deviation divided by the square root of the number of measurements, (SE)) (column 3).

PFR wavelength (nm)	$u_{\ln(I_0)}$ (aod)		u_{I_0} (%)	
	Coefficient of variation	Standard Error (norm. distribution)	Coefficient of variation	Standard Error (norm. distribution)
368	0.0013	0.00015	0.13	0.015
412	0.0015	0.00015	0.15	0.015
500	0.0014	0.00014	0.14	0.014
863	0.0017	0.00009	0.17	0.009

3) Rayleigh optical depth

The Rayleigh optical depth is calculated according to the formula of Bodhaine et al., 1999, or Nicolet, 1984. For the wavelength range between 300 nm and 1200 nm and at STP, the Rayleigh optical depth calculated with the two formulas, diverge by not more 0.001 in optical depth. Therefore, the standard uncertainty $u_{ray} = 0.001/\sqrt{3} = 5.8 * 10^{-4}$.

4) Ambient pressure

The ambient pressure is monitored with a calibrated air pressure sensor connected to the data acquisition system of the PFR unit. The corresponding standard uncertainty u_p is assumed to be less than 2 mbar. The main impact is on the Rayleigh correction, so at 500 nm, and using the formula of Bodhaine, the sensitivity coefficient $\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial P} = 1.4 * 10^{-4} \frac{1}{m}$

5) Ozone optical depth

The only sensitivity to atmospheric ozone is for the 500 nm channel of the PFR. For all other channels it is assumed to be negligible. The uncertainty of the total column ozone is assumed to be maximal 10 DU (uncertainty of the climatology used), which at 500 nm and using the absorption ozone cross-sections of Serdyuchenko et al., 2014 at -45 °C results in a standard expanded uncertainty of $u_{O_3} = \frac{3.16e^{-4}}{\sqrt{3}} = 6 * 10^{-5}$

6) Nitrogen Dioxide optical depth

The sensitivity to nitrogen dioxide is calculated similarly to the one for atmospheric ozone. This estimation applies to pristine conditions for example at Davos. Currently WORCC does not correct for NO₂, so the values are bias. It is calculated assuming a standard uncertainty of the nitrogen dioxide of 0.05 DU, which yields for the PFR channels (NO₂ absorption cross sections from Vandaele A.C. et al., (1996), at 294 K):

Channel /nm	u_{NO_2} assuming 0.05 DU
368	7e-4
412	8e-4
500	2.5e-4
862	0

7) Airmass

Aerosol airmass

Uncertainty in the optical path for aerosols (m) is calculated assuming the aerosol layer at 4 km and an uncertainty of ± 1 km of the layer height.

$$u_m = \Delta m / \sqrt{3} = 0.001 / \sqrt{3} = 5.7735e-04.$$

Ozone airmass

The height of the effective ozone layer is assumed to be at 22 km. The seasonal variability of this height depends on latitude and can be up to 4 km at low to middle latitudes. The corresponding uncertainty of the airmass calculation

$$u_{mO_3} = \Delta m_{O_3} / \sqrt{3} = 0.003 / \sqrt{3} = 0.0017$$

NO₂ airmass

The height of the peak concentration of NO₂ is assumed to be at the same height of the aerosol layer.

$$u_{mNO_2} = u_m$$

8) Wavelength offset and filter function

The uncertainty of the centroid wavelength λ and shape of the spectral responsivity function s^λ of the PFR filters introduces an uncertainty in the calculated optical depth of Rayleigh scattering and trace gases. The uncertainty assumed for the PFRs is based on the characterization result of PFR-N01 (Kouremeti et al., 2022) and PFR-L02. the observed differences in central wavelengths λ from the initial characterization are :

Channel	862 nm	500 nm	412 nm	368 nm
N01	1.42	0.29	0.62	0.01
L02	0.24	0.16	0.05	n/a

In the following table, the optical depth values at wavelength $\lambda=500$ nm for the measured relative response function s^λ of PFR-L02 are shown. The observed differences in optical depth for an estimated uncertainty in the centroid wavelength $u_\lambda=0.5$ nm ($\Delta x_s(s_{sim})$), and uncertainty in both λ and responsivity shape (Δx_s), represented by the differences of $s_{sim}^{\lambda+d\lambda}$ and s^λ are also shown. The expanded uncertainty of the OD is estimated by $(\Delta x_s / \sqrt{3}) * 2$ assuming that these differences ($d\lambda$, shape) are representative for 95% of PFR filters and a rectangular distribution.

	OD /cm (based on $s(\lambda)$)	$\Delta x_s(s_{sim})$ $x_s(s_{sim}^\lambda) - x_s(s_{sim}^{\lambda+d\lambda})$	Δx_s $x_s(s_{sim}^{\lambda+d\lambda}) - x_s(s^\lambda)$	Expanded uncertainty (k=2)	Weights units
Rayleigh /cm	142.571e-06	0.577e-06	3.209e-06	1.853e-06	hPa
Ozone /DU	35.151e-06	1.231e-06	1.502e-06	0.867e-06	DU
NO ₂ /DU	51.305e-04	1.428e-04	3.179e-04	1.835e-04	DU

9) Field of view stray light

The stray light from the finite field of view depends strongly on the amount and type of aerosols, which affects the forward scattering into the field of view of the instrument. For reference instruments and pristine conditions, the uncertainty is less than 0.5% of the measured AOD for all wavelengths.

Instruments performing measurements at areas with large particles (e.g. Deserts) would have additional uncertainties due to the larger effect of forward scattering. For that case we have calculated using two conditions/scenarios : AOD at 500 nm [0.15 0.4] (global average and relatively high) and two aerosol mean effective radii [0.2 1.5] (μm) (small and large particles). The forward scattered radiation is also a function of the airmass, with larger scattering at higher airmass (Cuevas et al., 2019)

The corresponding uncertainty is shown here for an airmass of 2, corresponding to a solar zenith angle of 60:

Channel /nm	Stray-light contribution in optical depth units			
	AOD @ 500 nm = 0.15		AOD @ 500 nm = 0.4	
	Aer. radii 0.2 μm	Aer. radii 1.5 μm	Aer. radii 0.2 μm	Aer. radii 1.5 μm
368	<0.0004	0.0075	<0.001	0.02
412	<0.0004	0.006	<0.001	0.016
500	<0.0004	0.0045	<0.001	0.012
862	<0.0004	0.003	<0.001	0.008

10) Window cleaning

For good cleaning (daily), the differences are less than 0.1% in signal levels.

11) Cloud contamination

The uncertainty described here is for best case scenarios for clear sky conditions. For this report, it is assumed to be zero. It is a difficult parameter to assess. For a network product it is non-zero, but for a reference measurement it can be assumed zero (best case conditions).

Uncertainty Budget

The uncertainty components depend on the airmass and specific wavelength. For this table, the compiled values are calculated for a solar zenith angle of 60° (airmass 2), a wavelength of 500 nm and a pressure of 1013.15 mbar, O₃=350 DU, N₀₂ =0.2 DU and AOD at 500 nm = 0.15 and Aer. radii 0.2 μm.

Table 1: Optical depth uncertainty budget for a reference precision filter radiometer (PFR) of GAWPFR-WORCC at 500 nm and at ground level for O₃=350 DU ,N₀₂ =0.2 DU and AOD at 500 nm = 0.15. The resulting optical depth uncertainty is unitless.

Parameter	Value xi	Uncertainty unit	Uncert type	Distribution	Nb. Deg. Freedom	Uncertainty u(xi)	Sensitivity coeff. C	C.u(xi)	Unit C.u(xi)
I	2	Relative	A	Normal	10	2.88E-03	0.50	1.44E-03	aod (dimensionless)
$I_{FOV_{strl}}^{rel}$	0	Relative				4.00E-04	0.50	2.00E-04	
$I_{Cleaning}^{rel}$	0	Relative		Rectangular		5.00E-04	0.50	2.50E-04	
I_{Clouds}^{rel}	0	Relative		Rectangular		0.00E+00	0.50	0.00E+00	
IO	3.7	Relative	A	Normal	30	1.40E-03	0.50	7.00E-04	
P	1013.15	mbar	B	Normal		2.00E+00	7.1E-5	1.41E-4	
τ_{ray}	0.1434	OD				5.8E-04	1.00	5.8E-04	
τ_{NO2}	0.001	OD	B	Rectangular		u(TC _{NO2})	1.00	2.49E-04	
τ_{O3}	0.0118	OD	B	Rectangular		u(TC _{O3})	1.00	1.80E-04	
M	2		B	Rectangular		5.77E-04	0.075	4.33E-05	
m_{ray}	2		B	Rectangular		5.77E-04	0.072	4.14E-05	
m_{O3}	2		B	Rectangular		1.70E-03	0.011	1.92E-05	
m_{NO2}	2		B	Rectangular		5.77E-04	0.001	5.76E-07	
$X_{S_{ray}}$	1.43e-04	OD/mbar	B	Rectangular		9.26e-07	1013.25	9.38e-04	
$X_{S_{O3}}$	3.5e-05	OD/DU	B	Rectangular		4.34e-07	350	1.52e-04	
$X_{S_{NO2}}$	5.1e-03	OD/DU	B	Rectangular		9.18e-05	0.200	1.84e-05	
Combined uncertainty								0.0020	
Expanded uncertainty (k=2)								0.0040	

AERONET- CE318 Master CIMEL

1) Direct solar irradiance measurement I

Uncertainty in measurements (u_{meas}) was calculated by means of the CV (standard deviation of triplets divided by the mean (triplet) value at 500 nm) for air mass lower than 2 of data at Izaña corresponding to the master #933 (CE318-TS, master Cimel at IZO) during year 2020 (48176 triplets). The result for 500 nm spectral band is 0.067%. We have also included in this term the contribution of out-of-band radiation and the uncertainty associated with dark signals:

$$C_{u,I} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{u_{dark}}{std_signal}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_{OOB}}{DCC_OOB}\right)^2 + u_{meas}}$$

Out of band contribution to signal (u_{OOB}/DC_OOB) is calculated to be <0.05% for the worst case (340nm channels) assuming out-of-band blocking of optical density 6. The contribution of dark counts has been estimated assuming a few counts out of 2^{22} counts (10^{-6}). Sensitivity coefficients for these terms have been set to 0.5.

2) Top of atmosphere solar irradiance

The statistical analysis of the long-term determination of the top-of-atmosphere irradiance value retrieved with the Cimel photometer by means of the Langley-plot procedure has been performed in Toledano et al. (2018). These authors studied the expected uncertainties in this calibration procedure in Mauna Loa and Izaña stations. According to their experience, the standard error of the IO's in a typical set of 20–30 Langley series is 0.4–0.5 % in the UV region, and 0.1-0.2% in the near-infrared wavelengths (870, 1020, 1640 nm).

$$u_{IO}=0.4-0.5\% \text{ in the UV}$$

$$u_{IO}=0.1-0.2\% \text{ (in the NIR)}$$

For 500 nm we have assumed a maximum $u_{IO}=0.005$, with a coefficient sensitivity of 0.5.

3) Atmospheric stability during the Langley

The assumption of atmospheric stability during the 1.5 – 2 h of the Langley period is very restrict, since the atmosphere displays a normal diurnal cycle in addition to sudden change in the aerosol load due to the arrival of different air masses or transported pollution. The selection of Izaña high mountain station ensures stability conditions are usually met, but the possible presence of a diurnal cycle of aerosols in Izaña and its possible impact has been studied in ESA. It is known that there exist an upward transport of humid and possibly contaminated air from lower levels during daylight, and a downward transport of dry and clean free troposphere air from higher levels at night. This pattern was studied by Rodriguez et al. (2009), who found a low amount of pre-existing particles for aerosol nucleation. In terms of PM₁₀ concentration, this cycle means a negligible rise from 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to nearly 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in the solar noon. This upward flow at daytime is mainly produced by the rise in SO₂, organic particles and other aerosol precursors concentration. This low concentration of accumulation and coarse-size aerosols above the thermal inversion favoured new particle formation (nanoparticles) by nucleation in the upward flows. This type of nanoparticles has not any effect in the AOD evolution. And this is the worst scenario, since the presence of this cycle is not expected to affect nocturnal measurements.

4) Rayleigh optical depth

Similarly to PFR-GAW, the Rayleigh optical depth is calculated according to the formula of Bodhaine, 1999, or Nicolet, 1984. For the wavelength range between 300 nm and 1700 nm and at STP, the Rayleigh optical depth calculated with the two formulas, diverge by not more 0.001 (Cuevas et al., 2019).

With this value, we can estimate the uncertainty in Rayleigh Cross sections to be:

$$u_{Ray}(500nm) = 0.001/\sqrt{3}$$

5) Ambient pressure

Latest versions of Cimels measure local pressure but older versions do not have a pressure sensor. Therefore the operational AERONET processing uses pressure from analysis fields (NCEP). In Gonzalez et al (2020) and Giles et al. (2019) we find that the expected error in P is 2 mbar. The main impact is on the Rayleigh correction, so at 500 nm, and using the formula of Bodhaine, the sensitivity coefficient

$$\frac{\partial \tau_{aod}}{\partial P} = 1.4 * 10^{-4} \frac{1}{m}$$

6) Ozone Optical Depth

In Cimel AERONET, ozone optical depth is used in the computation of AOD at 340, 500, and 675 nm and is retrieved using climatological the total column TOMS monthly average climatology (1978–2004) of O3 concentration at 1.00-1.25 degree spatial resolution (Giles et al. 2019). The O3 optical air mass is obtained using O3 scale height adjustment by latitude (Komhyr et al., 1989), and the O3 absorption coefficient is obtained from Burrows et al. (1999). Following Eck et al. (1999), maximum departures due to total column ozone variability (departures from climatological values by 50%) can lead to AOD uncertainties of 0.0036 at 340 nm, 0.0045 at 500 nm, and 0.0063 at 675 nm. Since these departures are maximum and much higher than expected, typical departures would be less than half this magnitude.

$$u_{O3}(500nm) = 0.0045/2/\sqrt{3}$$

7) Nitrogen Dioxide optical depth

Following Cuevas et al. (2019), differences in daily total NO2 between GAW-PFR and AERONET-Cimel is of the order of 10⁻³ for the 380 and 440 nm channels, while for the 500 nm channel it is of the order of 10⁻⁴. However, it should be noted that an impact on AOD calculation is expected when replicating similar analysis in highly NO2 polluted regions.

$$u_{NO2}(500nm) = 0.001/2/\sqrt{3}$$

8) Airmass

The same uncertainty analysis performed for PFR can be directly applied to Cimel.

9) Temperature correction

The correction formula is:

$$V = V' / \left(1 + C_1(T - 25) + C_2(T - 25)^2 \right)$$

The uncertainty in C1 and C2 derived from the fitting, the error in AOD produced by this correction is very small (Woolliams et al., 2018). At 20 °C this is effectively negligible (<0.02 % effect for 1020 nm on Si, and considerably less for other channels). By comparing two different characterizations of the same instrument, we achieved an uncertainty in the signal <0.04% for 1020nm Silicon, and <0.003% for all other channels, for the T range between –20 and 40 degrees.

10) Water vapor and CO₂-CH₄ correction

In Cimel AERONET, a correction factor for water vapor absorption is used in the computation of AOD at 1020 nm and 1640 nm. In the 1640 nm channel another correction factor is included to account for the absorption of mixed gases (CO₂ and CH₄). These correction factors are the following (Smirnov et al, 2004; and Giles et al., 2019):

$$\tau_{abs}(H_2O, 1020) = 0.0023 * PWV + 0.0002$$

$$\tau_{abs}(H_2O, 1640) = 0.0014 * PWV - 0.0003$$

Smirnov et al (2004) and Giles et al. (2019) set the uncertainties involved in the two coefficients of this correction for 1020 nm to 2% and 5%, respectively, being 5% and 2% for 1640 nm channel. The uncertainty in PWV (water vapour content) for sun photometers is estimated to be 10% by Schneider et al. (2010).

The correction included in 1640 nm channel is a formulation station-elevation (local pressure) dependent (Giles et al., 2019):

$$\tau_{abs}(CO_2, CH_4, 1640) = 0.0134 * P / P_0 \text{ where } P_0 \text{ is } 1013,25 \text{ hPa}$$

The uncertainty involved in the coefficient of the previous equation has been set to 4.5% by Smirnov et al. (2004).

$$u_{H_2O}(1020nm) = \sqrt{(0.02^2 + 0.10^2 + 0.05^2)} = 0.1136$$

$$u_{H_2O}(1640nm) = \sqrt{(0.05^2 + 0.10^2 + 0.02^2)} = 0.1136$$

$$u_{gases}(1640nm) = \sqrt{(0.045^2 + 8.66E - 6^2)} = 0.045$$

where 8.66E-6 comes from u(P) previously calculated.

Taking into account that H₂O and mixed gases absorption is negligible for 500nm reference wavelength the uncertainty due to these components at this wavelength is zero.

11) Field of view stray light

Relative errors in AOD due to scattered radiation within the Cimel FOV for different aerosol effective radius and AOD values (0.1-1.0) were evaluated in Cuevas et al. (2019). These authors found that the relative errors in AOD depends strongly on the particle size but it is fairly constant for each value of AOD considered.

Channel /nm	Relative error in AOD due to stray-light contribution in %, m=2
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	AOD @ 500 nm = 0.15		AOD @ 500 nm = 0.4	
	Aer. radii 0.2 μm	Aer. radii 1.5 μm	Aer. radii 0.2 μm	Aer. radii 1.5 μm
380	-0.1%	-1.8%	-0.05%	-1.6%
440	-0.1%	-1.6%	-0.05%	-1.7%
500	-0.1%	-1.1%	-0.05%	-0.9%
870	-0.2%	-0.38%	-0.1%	-0.32%

13) Wavelength offset and filter functions

This was not explicitly taken into account for this type of radiometer, so the values determined for the PFR in the previous section were used.

14) Window cleaning

Double collimator check to monitor window dirtiness, reject data if $\Delta\text{AOD}(1020) \times \text{airmass} > 0.06$. No expected uncertainty is expected for this term.

15) Cloud contamination

Cloud-screened data is used for AOD calculation, so uncertainty associated to cloud contamination is assumed to be zero.

Uncertainty Budget

The uncertainty components depend on the airmass and specific wavelength. For this table, the compiled values are calculated for a solar zenith angle of 60°, a wavelength of 500 nm and a pressure of 1013.15 mbar.

Table 2 Uncertainty budget for a reference CE318 CIMEL radiometer from AERONET and at ground level for O3=350 DU ,N02 =0.2 DU and AOD at 500 nm = 0.15. The resulting optical depth uncertainty is unitless.

Parameter	Value xi	Uncertainty unit	Uncert type	Distribution	Nb. Deg. Freedom	Uncertainty u(xi)	Sensitivity coeff. C	C.u(xi)
triplets (48176)	m<2	Relative	A	Normal	2	$0.00067/\sqrt{2}=4.74E-4$	0.5	2.37E-4
dark		Voltages	B	Triangular		$10^{-6}/\sqrt{6}=4.08E-7$	0.5	2.04E-7
OOB	OD=6	Relative	B	Triangular		$0.0005/\sqrt{6}=2.04E-4$	0.5	1.03E-4
Temperature		Relative (RE)	B	Normal		0.00003	0.5	1.5E-5
FOV		Relative (RE)	B	Normal		0.001	0.5	5.0E-4
Atmospheric Stability		Relative	B	Normal		0		0
l ₀	m: 2-5	Relative	B	Normal		0.005	0.5	2.50E-3
P	1013.15	mbar	B	Normal		2	7.1E-5	1.41E-4
τ _{ray}	0.1434					8.66E-6, 5.77 E-4	1.00	5.8E-4
τ _{N02}	0.001		B	Rectangular		2.88E-5	1.00	2.88E-5
τ _{O3}	0.0118		B	Rectangular		1.3E-3	1.00	1.3E-3
τ _{H2O}	PWV=1 cm	cm	B	Rectangular		0		0
τ _{gases}			B	Rectangular		0		0
M	2		B	Rectangular		5.77E-4	0.075	4.33E-5
m _{ray}	2		B	Rectangular		5.77E-4	0.072	4.14E-5
m _{O3}	2		B	Rectangular		1.70E-3	0.011	1.92E-5
m _{N02}	2		B	Rectangular		5.77E-4	0.001	5.76E-7
X _{Sray}	1.43e-04	OD/mbar	B	Rectangular		9.26e-07	1013.25	9.38e-04
X _{so3}	3.5e-05	OD/DU	B	Rectangular		4.34e-07	350	1.52e-04
X _{SNO2}	5.1e-03	OD/DU	B	Rectangular		9.18e-05	0.200	1.84e-05
cleaning			B	Rectangular		0		0
Cloud contamination			B	Rectangular		0		0
Combined uncertainty								0.0031
Expanded uncertainty (k=2)								0.0062

SKYNET- POM Prede reference radiometers at MAPP

1) Direct solar irradiance measurement

The measurement relative uncertainty $u_{r,I}$ has been estimated from three different relative terms: $u_{r,dark}$, $u_{r,STD}$ and $u_{r,point}$, given in table 3.1 for the wavelengths of the reference POM01 instrument used in the tests. The $u_{r,dark}$ term is calculated from the ratio between series of measurements of dark signal and consecutive sun measurements. The $u_{r,std}$ term is computed as the ratio between the standard deviation and average of series of consecutive sun spectral measurements. The $u_{r,point}$ term is calculated as the ratio between the standard deviation of measurements performed around the sun, assuming a maximum pointing error of 0.1° (probably overestimated, as sun pointing in reference POM periodically adjusted to ensure a pointing error lower than 0.03°). The three relative terms are taken into account in the formula below for the relative standard uncertainty estimation.

$$u_{r,I} = \sqrt{(u_{r,dark})^2 + (u_{r,std} / \sqrt{10})^2 + (u_{r,point} / \sqrt{9})^2}$$

Table 3.1: Relative total uncertainty for the direct solar measurements.

λ (nm)	$U_{r,I}$ (%)
340	0.80
400	0.47
500	0.21
675	0.27
870	0.67
1020	0.23

2) Top of atmosphere solar irradiance

For the reference POM radiometer from CNR, the standard Langley plot calibration was performed at Izaña campaign. The coefficient of variation (standard deviation / mean) for 6 different Langley plots was estimated 2.5%, 1.1%, 0.41%, 0.16%, 0.44% and 0.66%, for channels 340, 400, 500, 675, 870 and 1020 nm respectively.

However, the Improved Langley Plot (ILP) method is usually employed for POM radiometers (Campanelli et al., 2007) and will be adopted in this report for the two reference instruments. In SKYNET, the coefficient of variation CV(%) is usually reported associated to monthly I_0 values. The averaged CV is shown in Table 3.2, using 14 different monthly calibrations, for the wavelengths of the reference instruments. For 500 nm, the CV is 0.87%.

Table 3.2: Relative uncertainty terms and total standard uncertainty.

Λ (nm)	CV (%)
340	1.3
400	1.3
500	0.87
675	0.66
870	0.60
1020	0.69

3) Ambient pressure

Old POM radiometers did not include a barometer unless requested by the user (not available in our case) but simultaneous measurements from collocated barometers can be used for reference instruments. At Rome site, a Vaisala PTB 200 digital barometer is available. Its specifications claim an accuracy of 0.01 hPa. At Valencia site, a Vaisala WXT520 sensor is available. Its specifications claim an accuracy of 0.5 hPa in the temperature range 0°C to +30°C, and 1.0 hPa for the temperature interval -52°C to +60°C. However, given that no recent calibration is available, we will assume a maximum uncertainty similar to AERONET master CIMEL cases ($u_{a,p} = 2$ mbar).

4) Rayleigh optical depth

The Rayleigh optical depth is calculated according to the formula of Bodhaine (1999) or Nicolet (1984). For the wavelength range between 300 nm and 1700 nm and at STP, the Rayleigh optical depth calculated with the two formulas, diverge by not more 0.001, as in the case of Cimel. Therefore, the absolute standard uncertainty of the Rayleigh cross section is calculated as $u_{xray} = 0.001/\sqrt{3} = 5.8 * 10^{-4}$, similarly to PFR-GAW and AERONET master CIMEL cases. The Rayleigh optical depth uncertainty is calculated including the ambient pressure uncertainty: $6.4 * 10^{-4}$.

5) Ozone optical depth

For the analysis of reference POM radiometers, ozone columnar burden from OMI can be used, assuming an uncertainty of 2.2% based on Nuñez et al. (2016). But if only a daily value is available, then we assume a rough maximum 10%. Use of data from collocated ground based instruments (Brewer) when available, would bring a lower uncertainty.

The ozone cross sections used are those published by Gueymard (1995), that result of merging previous spectroscopic laboratory datasets at different bands, and smoothed at 1 nm resolution, with corresponding corrections to account for the effective temperature (Gueymard, 1995). Unfortunately, no information is provided about the corresponding uncertainty. Therefore, similar uncertainty estimation than for PFR-GAW is assumed.

6) Nitrogen Dioxide optical depth

Nominal values are used depending on standard atmospheres, with values about 0.2 DU (Gueymard, 1995) but an impact on AOD is expected for polluted environments. At the moment, a maximum uncertainty of about 0.1 DU has been assumed, it is, maximum relative uncertainty of 50%.

The NO₂ cross sections result of merging previous spectroscopic laboratory datasets at different bands, and smoothed at 1 nm resolution, with corresponding corrections to account for the effective temperature (Gueymard, 1995). No estimation of the corresponding uncertainty of the coefficients nor the correction method is provided so we assume a similar uncertainty than for PFR-GAW case.

7) Water vapor optical depth

The method to account for the water vapor absorption and the correspondent water vapor optical depth correction is based on reports from Gueymard (1995). For reference POM radiometers, ancillary data can be used, although typically standard atmosphere values are input. For the 500 nm channel, the water vapour absorption effect is negligible.

8) Other gases optical depth

Currently, no optical depth for other gases is calculated, and their uncertainty is not accounted for.

9) Airmass

The air mass for molecular, aerosol, and NO₂ is that of Kasten and Young (1989) formula. For the ozone optical mass, the formula of Komhyr (1989) is used instead, with the altitude of the ozone layer being calculated with a simple formula dependent with the site latitude. Independent formulae for Rayleigh, NO₂, ozone and aerosol are also available (Gueymard, 2001), that take into account the atmosphere curvature and the vertical distribution of the corresponding scatterers and absorbers, but no estimation of their uncertainty is available. Comparison of air masses obtained by Kasten and Young (1989) with Gueymard (2001), and also by Komhyr (1989) with Gueymard (2001), at a zenith angle of 60°, shows the corresponding standard uncertainty, calculated as $u_m = \Delta m / \sqrt{3}$.

Table 3.9: uncertainties for air mass components

Attenuator	u_m
Rayleigh	0.00016
Aerosol	0.0024
O ₃	0.0032
NO ₂	0.0056

10) Sensor temperature effect

The Prede POM radiometer keeps the optical sensor at constant temperature. The same temperature is used for the calibration and signal measurement, meaning that the effect of temperature should be negligible, as long as the temperature is actually kept constant in reference instruments. Failure to control temperature would affect the AOD uncertainty, mainly for 1020 nm.

11) Field of view stray light

The FOV for the Prede POM radiometers is 1.0°, lower than the 1.2° FOV for the CIMEL instrument. Therefore, in the absence of specific computations for the Prede POM, we assume the values previously stated for the Cimel instrument (Cuevas et al., 2019).

Table 3.11: relative error in AOD due to stray-light contribution

Channel /nm	Relative error in AOD due to stray-light contribution in %			
	AOD @ 500 nm = 0.15		AOD @ 500 nm = 0.4	
	Aer. Radii 0.2 μm	Aer. Radii 1.5 μm	Aer. Radii 0.2 μm	Aer. Radii 1.5 μm
380	-0.1%	-1.8%	-0.05%	-1.6%
500	-0.1%	-1.1%	-0.05%	-0.9%
870	-0.2%	-0.38%	-0.1%	-0.32%

12) Wavelength offset and filter functions

This was not explicitly taken into account for this type of radiometer, so the values determined for the PFR in the previous section were used.

13) Window cleaning

Our tests for a reference radiometer with daily cleaning showed an effect of about 0.05% in the direct irradiance. The assumed standard relative uncertainty is $u_{r,wc} = 0.1\%$ for a 2-day cleaning routine in the reference radiometers, in terms of irradiance measurement.

14) Cloud contamination

Cloud contamination is assumed to be inexistent during well controlled conditions such as those for a reference instrument during field campaigns and after application of cloud screening algorithms.

Uncertainty Budget

The uncertainty components depend on the airmass and specific wavelength. For this table, the compiled values are calculated for a solar zenith angle of 60°, a wavelength of 500 nm and a pressure of 1013.15 mbar.

Table 3: Optical depth uncertainty budget for a Prede radiometer of SKYNET at 500 nm and at ground level for $O_3=350$ DU, $NO_2=0.2$ DU and AOD at 500 nm = 0.15. The resulting optical depth uncertainty is unitless.

Parameter	Value xi	Uncertainty unit	Uncert type	Distribution	Nb. Deg. Freedom	Uncertainty u(xi)	Sensitivity coeff. C	C.u(xi)
I		Relative	A	normal		0.0021	0.5	1.1E-3
$I_{FOV_{strl}}^{rel}$		Relative				0.0011	0.5	5.5E-4
$I_{Cleaning}^{rel}$		Relative				0.001	0.5	5.0E-4
I_0		Relative	A	normal		0.0087	0.5	4.4E-3
P	1013.25	mbar	B	rectangular	2			
τ_{Ray}	0.1434	OD				0.00060	1.0	6.0E-4
τ_{O_3}	0.0118	OD	B	rectangular		0.00068	1.0	6.8E-4
τ_{NO_2}	0.001	OD	B	rectangular		0.00029	1.0	2.9E-4
m	2		B	Rectangular		0.0024	0.075	1.8E-4
m_{ray}	2		B	Rectangular		0.00016	0.072	1.2E-5
m_{O_3}	2		B	Rectangular		0.0032	0.011	3.5E-5
m_{NO_2}	2		B	rectangular		0.0056	0.001	5.6E-6
XSRay	1.43e-04	OD/mbar	B	Rectangular		9.26e-07	1013.25	9.38e-04
XSo3	3.5e-05	OD/DU	B	Rectangular		4.34e-07	350	1.52e-04
XSN02	5.1e-03	OD/DU	B	Rectangular		9.18e-05	0.200	1.84e-05
Combined uncertainty								0.0048
Expanded uncertainty (k=2)								0.0096

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